

Systematic use of orthologous information to improve the phylogeny of paralogous genes

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Abstract

Gene duplication is one of the main driving forces of evolution. Yet, establishing reliable phylogenetic relationships among paralogous genes remains a challenging task. Tree reconstruction can be significantly improved by increasing the amount of supporting data. In the case of paralogous gene reconstruction, it is, however, difficult to increase the amount of data without having to build extremely large gene trees in order to simultaneously infer orthologous and paralogous relationships. In this study, we focused on a specific scenario, in which one attempts to reconstruct a paralogous tree whose duplications took place before the last unique common ancestor of the considered genomes. In this precise situation, we show that the information across the sibling genomes can be combined either using a supermatrix or a supertree approach and that yields significant topological improvements. As a support to our claim, we constructed a simulated dataset featuring 500 families and complemented this analysis with 41 empirical datasets. The empirical validation was carried out by showing that when combining the information across genomes, one can increase the topological similarity between minimum evolution and maximum likelihood trees by enriching the genomic information. At a time when accurate orthologous assignments can be inferred using direct full genome alignments, our approach provides a new and efficient way to integrate large amounts of genomic data into accurate paralogous phylogenetic trees.

Introduction

Homology is a fundamental concept of evolutionary biology that refers to the common origin of traits including genes. According to the mode of descent, this common origin can be further divided into orthology, which refers to genes derived from speciation events, and paralogy, which refers to genes derived from gene duplication events (Fitch 1970). The phylogenetic analysis of these two homology subtypes can shed light either on species or on genes' evolutionary relationships respectively. Paralogs, unlike orthologs, do not often share similar functions despite their common ancestry (Ohno 1970; Birchler and Yang 2022). Specifically, gene duplication creates redundancy that is typically not favoured in living systems and, for this reason, the fate of the duplicate gene is either to become a pseudogene through genetic inactivation - and eventually disappear so as to constitute a gene loss - or diverge from the parental gene so as to acquire a new function (neofunctionalization). Neofunctionalization can take many forms, the most common being subfunctionalization (Hurst and Smith 1998; Kleinjan et al. 2008). Changes in substrate or interaction specificity are also possible and albeit less common, they have been shown to be usually associated with a process of positive selection, that is to say, a higher than expected fixation rate for non-synonymous mutations (Barkman et al. 2007). There also exists the possibility for the duplicated child and its parent to both adopt new evolutionary trajectories under the pressure of their mutual competition (Baker et al. 2013). For all these reasons, various paralogs are often evolving under different evolutionary clocks, a process known as heterotachy (Lopez et al. 2002), or even undergoing gene conversion (Chen et al. 2007). All these processes tend to affect one another, thus, making accurate phylogenetic reconstruction all the more challenging. This is a rather unfortunate situation, since the accurate reconstruction of paralogous phylogenetic trees would provide us with a unique access to the emergence of molecular functions. We show here how the systematic use of orthologous information makes it possible to resolve the gene trees of ancient duplications when these duplications predate speciation (Fig. 1a).

One of the main issues when reconstructing phylogenies is the presence of a sufficient evolutionary signal to support the resolution of the underlying evolutionary tree. The amount of signal depends on the amount of data and on its suitability. For instance, when computing a phylogenetic tree from a multiple sequence alignment (MSA), the usable data amounts to the number of usable sites (columns) in the MSA. When working on the orthologous representative of a gene family, this quantity is bounded by the average protein length. The growing availability of complete genome sequences has provided ways to mitigate this limitation using two major strategies. The first one is known as supermatrix (SM) (Kluge 1989; de Queiroz and Gatesy 2007). It involves collecting a set of MSAs, each featuring orthologous genes gathered across the same species and concatenating them before estimating a tree while treating the concatenated MSAs as a single long MSA. Under this formulation, the number of sites increases with the number of concatenated genes. This approach was shown to allow the resolution of complex regions in the Tree of Life such as the bee (Hedtke et al. 2013) and the avian (Burleigh et al. 2015) evolutionary histories. The second approach is named supertree (ST). It relies on a similar collection of MSAs, but rather than being concatenated, these MSAs are individually resolved into phylogenetic trees and these trees are then combined into a supertree using specific algorithms such as SuperFine or ASTRAL (Swenson et al. 2012; Mirarab et al. 2014).

To our knowledge, the supertree and supermatrix approaches have not been applied to the resolution of paralogous phylogenies. One reason is that, while in Tree-of-Life supermatrix concatenation the rationale for concatenating genes from the same genome is obvious, in the case of a paralogous gene tree it is not entirely clear how to meaningfully increase the number of sites. We are arguing here that the number of usable sites can be increased by focusing on paralogous genes duplicated before the speciation of the considered species (i.e. duplications already present in the last unique common ancestor). Under this specific condition, it is possible to concatenate the MSAs carried out within each genome, provided

the orthologous genes are on the same line of the concatenated matrix. The supertree methods can be adapted in a similar way. In this work, we have assessed the relative merits of the supertree and supermatrix approach under the above scenario.

One may argue about some level of circularity, since establishing an orthologous relationship is often reported as the deconvolution of complete gene trees featuring mixes of orthologs and paralogs (Heller et al. 2019). Yet, the use of genomic location and synteny conservation has also been reported as an alternative and powerful way to establish and support orthologous relationships, especially among closely related species. The growing density of the Tree of Life, fueled by high throughput flagship projects, such as the Earth BioGenome Project (Lewin et al. 2018), is rapidly offering effective ways of inferring orthology without the requirement of phylogenetic reconstruction (Kaduk and Sonnhammer 2017; Train et al. 2017). It is, therefore, a valid assumption that, within a large multi-gene family, trustworthy classes of orthologs may be available even if an equivalent gene tree is not. We have been working under this assumption and have developed a framework, in which this approach can be applied to the systematic analysis of paralogous protein sequences evolution (Fig. 1b).

Results

Application to simulated protein families

To validate the effectiveness of the supermatrix and supertree approaches on paralogous genes, we used an existing setup (Sloutsky and Naegle 2019) (see Materials and Methods) to simulate the evolution of 500 protein families containing 15 paralogs each across 25 species with duplications set within the last unique common ancestor of these 25 species. This procedure generated a very large MSA per family from which the orthologs and the paralogs can be unambiguously extracted. For each family, we collected 25 MSAs (one per simulated genome), with each MSA featuring the alignment of the 15 paralogs contained in the considered genome. The MSAs were then both used to estimate phylogenetic trees (Supertree) and concatenated so as to arrange for all the 1-to-1 orthologs to be on the same MSA line (Supermatrix). Because the genes arose from a simulation, the true paralogous topology is known. Based on this, we attempted to reconstruct this topology from the complete set of concatenated MSAs. In order to show the contribution of concatenation towards the correct phylogenetic resolution, we downsampled the analysis by randomly collecting (drawing without replacement) a number of columns equal to the average length of the 25 MSAs ('sampling units'). Their main benefit over the original MSAs is to allow the inclusion of some representative sampling of all possible genome concatenations without having to enumerate the full list of combinations (i.e. genome 1 with 2, genome 1 with 3, etc). In practice, these units can be generated by shuffling all the columns and splitting the resulting MSA into 25 blocks. One can then measure the effect of adding these blocks one at a time. Sampling can be refined by reiterating this process (10 times in the current study). These alignment sampling units served as input for the phylogenetic inference of the paralogous sequences using minimum evolution trees (ME) (FastME (Lefort et al. 2015)) and maximum likelihood trees (ML) (RAxML (Stamatakis 2014)). The trees were either computed onto the individual sampling units and combined (supertree), or they were estimated on the concatenated units (supermatrix), thus, resulting in four different trees for

each dataset: (1) Supertree-ME, (2) Supertree-ML, (3) Supermatrix-ME and (4) Supermatrix-ML. It should be pointed out that the supertrees were estimated using the SuperFine+MRP supertree strategy rather than ASTRAL, which is often considered the state-of-the-art. We did so, because ASTRAL's overall strategy requires a complete gene tree from which a multi-species coalescence method is then used to extract both the paralogous and the orthologous information. Yet, the computation of a complete gene tree can be a serious limitation, especially when dealing with large families and numerous genomes. We are arguing here that by exploiting genome based orthologous assignments and processing each genome independently, a large-scale genomics approach is feasible at a significantly lower computational cost.

To assess the performance of our proposed strategy, we compared the resulting trees to the reference using the Robinson and Foulds (RF) (Robinson and Foulds 1981) distance metric, which estimates the fraction of branches differing between two alternative trees of the same taxa. Our results show that in the four considered protocols, congruence increases with the number of incorporated units as reflected by lower RF measurements (Fig. 2, Table 1). As one would expect, ML significantly outperforms ME (0.12 and 0.16 respectively for the Supermatrix-Unit-25, the best performing protocol, Wilcoxon test p-value = $1e-08$). We also found a slight benefit in the MSA concatenation over the supertree protocol with Supermatrix-ML inducing slightly higher RF differences than Supertree-ML (0.18 and 0.17 respectively). These differences are consistent with the observation that over the 500 datasets supermatrix outperforms supertree slightly more often than the other way around (43.00% and 30.40% respectively Wilcoxon test p-value = 0.09 on ML and 47.00% and 32.80% respectively on ME, Wilcoxon test p-value = 0.19 on ME, Supplementary Fig. 1, Supplementary Table 1).

One of the benefits of the supermatrix protocol is that it lends itself to a standard Felsenstein bootstrap analysis (Felsenstein 1985). Of course, the MSA units are explicitly

non-independent (i.e. they would be identical if the considered genomes had just undergone speciation) and one therefore needs a correction for the non-independence of these MSA units. The ideal solution would be to estimate the amount of unique information contributed by each genome using a weighting scheme like Voronoi (Sibbald and Argos 1990), but a simpler more conservative approach can be achieved by considering that given N genomes, each MSA contributes 1/N of the global signal. This assumption naturally leads to sampling bootstrap replicates having the average length of the original 25 MSAs. Even when applying this correction, the average branch bootstrap support increases monotonically with the number of concatenated units and it does so along with the fraction of branches having a bootstrap support higher than 70% (Supplementary Fig. 2). It is worth mentioning that the increase in branch bootstrap support is more important on ML trees than on ME trees. On the ME trees, the fraction of branches with a support higher than 70% increases from 39% to 48%, while on ML trees similar measurements indicate an increase from 45% to 59% (Supplementary Table 2-3).

Altogether these results support our hypothesis that the reconstruction of paralogous phylogenies can be improved by combining related data collected across genomes, and that the supermatrix and supertree protocols lend themselves to orthology-based concatenation/combination. The simulations carried out here also suggest a slight but non-significant superiority of the supermatrix approach.

Application to mouse multigene protein families

The empirical validation of phylogenetic reconstruction methods is often hampered by the lack of experimentally validated reference phylogenetic trees. In the case of paralogous trees, this limitation is worsened by the lack of a universal Tree-of-Life scenario (i.e. within a genome, every paralogous tree is potentially unique). We addressed this issue by taking advantage of the fact that ME is established to have a lower resolute capacity than ML

(Guindon and Gascuel 2003; Guindon et al. 2010). Taking this into account, one can estimate a reference ML tree (i.e. the ML paralogous tree in any of the considered species) and then measure on ME trees the impact of the combination of sampling units from the other species with respect to their capacity of recapitulating this reference ML tree. If congruence between ME and ML increases with the number of units, then one can conclude that the phylogenetic resolute potential of the data is indeed increased by supermatrix concatenation or supertree combination.

We selected the mouse sequences to estimate the reference ML trees, because it is the species whose annotation comes along with the largest amount of orthologous information. We then used PFAM (Mistry et al. 2021) (<https://pfam.xfam.org/>) to identify protein families with at least 10 paralogs so that each of the paralogs had a 1-to-1 ortholog (as defined by OMA) reported in at least 6 species. In total, we identified 41 families meeting these selection criteria. For each family, 6 MSAs were computed (one for each of the genomes in which the 1-to-1 orthologs had been identified) and these MSAs were eventually used to infer supertree and supermatrix trees using a procedure similar to the one deployed when doing the simulations. It is important to stress that the mouse dataset used to estimate the reference is not part of the 6 genomes datasets combined using ME methods. Our results indicate that this empirical dataset recapitulates the main observations made on the simulations (Fig. 3, Supplementary Fig. 3, Table 2). Indeed, the concatenation followed by processing with ME allows the supermatrix and the supertree protocols to reconstruct a sizable fraction of the ML topologies. As expected, the level of recapitulation increases with the number of combined units. Similarly to the analysis of the simulated datasets, we observed a slight but non-significant benefit in the supermatrix over the supertree protocol with Supermatrix-ME inferring topologies with higher RF differences than their Supertree-ME counterparts (0.11 and 0.09, Wilcoxon test p-value = 0.55). We further analysed these results by dissecting them at the level of each dataset and found out that in 25 out of 41 datasets (60.98%) Supermatrix-ME outperforms Supertree-ME, while the opposite happens

in 13 datasets (31.71%) with 3 datasets having identical supermatrix and supertree topologies (7.31%) (Supplementary Fig. 4, Supplementary Table 4).

Discussion

In this study we explored the possibility of enriching the phylogenetic analysis of paralogous genes using orthology information. We explored the potential of two strategies based on either concatenation (supermatrix) or supertree estimation. Both make it possible to extend any given paralogous dataset using information gathered from other genomes. The only requirement is the availability of trustworthy orthologous information. The rationale underlying our approach is the notion that distinct species can be used as independent estimators when measuring divergence within a protein family. Specifically, let us consider a family of paralogous genes already present in the last unique common ancestor of a set of related species. At the time of divergence from this common ancestor, the paralogous genes will differ by the mutations they previously acquired after the duplications they arose from. Just before the first speciation, these mutations constitute the optimal signal available for the reconstruction of this paralogous gene family tree. After speciation, this signal cannot be improved and will gradually be degraded over time, while each member of the family acquires new mutations. The rates of this acquisition may vary across members, across genomes and even through time. In the end, the whole process will eventually lead to the accumulation of confounding signals such as multiple hits or reversions. Yet, this degradation process will take place simultaneously and independently across all the considered genomes. Our approach is based on the assumption that these independent evolutionary replicates can be combined and that this combination can be used to mitigate some of the confounding effects so as to reconstruct more accurate paralogous trees.

Our data combination strategy assumes that the signal contained in the phylogenetic tree of a single paralogous set (i.e. all paralogs within a single genome) can be enhanced by combining it with similar orthologous datasets collected in related genomes. Our simulations support this hypothesis and show that genomes having diverged from a common ancestor can jointly contribute to estimating an ancestral pattern of gene duplication. We also

observed on the simulated data that ML trees benefit more than ME trees from the combination. This observation is consistent with the expectation that ML has better capacities than ME to reconcile the evolutionary signal contained in an MSA with a tree and it indirectly supports our claim that the combination effectively results in an improved phylogeny. We further confirmed these results on experimental data by showing that our combination protocol is able to increase the resolute capacity of ME and bring it closer to ML. Our results are consistent for both supermatrix and supertree protocols, but also suggested a slight but non-significant superiority of the supermatrix concatenation.

As it is, the method lends itself to many important applications. Various major projects are now under way to produce unprecedented numbers of animal genomes (Lewin et al. 2018). These genomes harbour many important multi-gene protein families such as kinases or ABC transporters to cite the largest ones. In order to make the most out of these genomes, it has become a pressing issue to figure out how the data they contain can be combined in the most effective way so as to cast some evolutionary light on key molecular processes. With the largest accurate phylogenetic trees limited to about 10,000 taxa, it is increasingly clear that the current phylogenetic methods do not have the potential to scale with the future genomic data, as it would require gene trees featuring hundreds of thousands of sequences, if not more. Our method has a much better scale up potential, because it uses the orthologous assignments to parallelize the problem and deal independently with each genome before combining their information content into a final model. This approach could help elucidate some fine details of gene duplication, which constitutes an essential step towards our understanding of molecular functions evolution.

Of course, many hurdles remain. For instance, the validation carried out in this work has been focused on simplified gene evolution models that exclude gene loss and post-speciation duplications. This is arguably the most serious limitation of our approach, but at the same time, this limitation defines a scope. Given any set of paralogous genes and

their associated genome, there will always exist a subset of related species sharing a common ancestor, in which a given pattern of duplication was already present. The method we propose will, therefore, either be used to reconstruct the tree of the current paralogs, when all of them were already present in the last unique ancestor, or will provide an entry point towards the resolution of deep nodes connecting the ancestral genes, when these genes have kept undergoing complex evolutionary patterns. Another serious limitation is the assumption that trustworthy orthologous inference can be done based on syntenic analysis. There are good reasons to believe that the current pace of full genome sequencing and the impact of long read assembly technology will make this last assumption realistic very soon, but it is also clear that further work will be required to explore the influence of more complex evolutionary scenarios on the paralogous supermatrix/supetree procedures described here.

Materials and Methods

Simulated datasets

The simulated datasets were assembled using a paralogs evolution simulation protocol (Sloutsky and Naegle 2019). In total 500 protein families were simulated. For each family, a random paralogous tree containing 15 genes was generated and part of the Ensembl Compara species tree that contained 25 species was integrated into each leaf representing ortholog divergence. Divergence times for the species trees were retrieved from timetree.org (Hedges et al. 2015; Kumar et al. 2017) and used to adjust the corresponding branch lengths. Sequence evolution was simulated over each resulting phylogeny using indel-Seq-Gen (v2.1.0) (Strope et al. 2007) under the JTT substitution model seeded with an alignment of human tyrosine kinase domains consisting of 24 parts based on local sequence similarity and analysis of solved tyrosine kinase structures. Each part was assigned a substitution rate scaling factor and an insertion/deletion model to match the degree of conservation and solvent exposure in solved structures. We decreased the number of these parts so as to form five simulated family groups (100 families per group) each featuring between 2 and 6 parts of the 24 parts from the initial alignment. We did so in order to increase the diversity of the simulated datasets, reduce the computational cost and evaluate the potential effect of alignment length to our framework. Moreover, in order for the simulation to meet the requirement of our analysis we modified the evolutionary parameters so as to maintain sequence identity at 20% or more among paralogs.

Mouse empirical datasets

Mouse empirical datasets were assembled by scanning PFAM (release 32) (Finn et al. 2016) for multigene families containing at least 40 mouse entries. We then carried out further filtering so as to collect PFAM families featuring at least 10 mouse entries, belonging to an OMA group (release Dec2018) (Altenhoff et al. 2021) and having 1-to-1 orthologs in at least 6 species other than mouse. This process led to the collection of 646 paralogous sequences

with 1-to-1 orthologs among 6 species (in total 3,876 protein sequences) that formed 41 datasets.

Multiple Sequence Alignments and Phylogenetic tree inference

MSAs were computed using T-Coffee v.13.45.57.844f401 (Notredame et al. 2000). The phylogenetic inference was carried out by FastME version 2.1.6.1 (Lefort et al. 2015) for the distance-based (ME) trees and by RAxML version 8.2.12 (Stamatakis 2014) for the maximum likelihood (ML) trees.

Supermatrix protocol

MSAs corresponding to all the paralogs in a considered genome were collected and multiply aligned using T-Coffee. In each alignment the sequences were ordered in such a way that the 1-to-1 orthologs appear on the same line. The MSAs were then concatenated and the columns shuffled. The sampling units were generated by splitting the full shuffled MSA into blocks having the average length of the original MSAs. The sampling units were eventually concatenated one unit at a time, and a phylogenetic tree subsequently estimated on the concatenated units. The procedure was repeated ten times for each family. The described supermatrix protocol was implemented in a custom python script available from the following Github repository (<https://github.com/athbaltzis/paralogs-nf>).

Supertree protocol

The supertree protocol used exactly the same procedure for generating sampling units as the one described in the supermatrix protocol. However, these units, rather than being concatenated, were used to generate phylogenetic trees with either RaxML or FastME. The resulting trees were then combined, one at a time, so as to generate the supertrees. The supertrees themselves were produced using SuperFine version 1.0 (Swenson et al. 2012).

Phylogenetic tree comparisons and bootstrap analysis

To compare the phylogenetic trees we used the Robinson-Foulds distance (Robinson and Foulds 1981) as implemented in the `RF.dist` function of the R package `phangorn` 2.7.0 (Schliep 2011). The bootstrap support was measured using the function `prop.clades` of the R package `ape` 5.5 (Paradis and Schliep 2019).

Computation

All computation was carried out on a cluster running Scientific Linux release 7.2. The alignments and the phylogenetic inference were run within a container based on Scientific Linux 7 operating system. The whole computational pipeline was implemented in the Nextflow language (Di Tommaso et al. 2017) and was deployed in a containerized form using Singularity.

Display items

Table 1 | Average Robinson-Foulds (RF) distance between each of the 4 methods and the reference phylogeny for the trees computed on one alignment unit and on the combination of all the alignment units as well as its difference over 500 simulated datasets.

Method	RF - Unit 1	RF - Unit 25	RF Difference
<i>Supermatrix-ME</i>	0.36	0.16	0.20
<i>Supertree-ME</i>	0.36	0.17	0.19
<i>Supermatrix-ML</i>	0.30	0.12	0.18
<i>Supertree-ML</i>	0.30	0.13	0.17

Table 2 | Average Robinson-Foulds (RF) distance between Supermatrix-ME or Supertree-ME topologies without including mouse paralogs multiple sequence alignments and the RAxML trees computed only on the multiple sequence alignments of the mouse paralogs per family (ML-MOUSE) using one alignment unit and the combination of all the alignment units as well as its difference over 41 multigene mouse datasets.

Method	RF - Unit 1	RF - Unit 6	RF Difference
<i>Supermatrix-ME</i>	0.51	0.39	0.11
<i>Supertree-ME</i>	0.51	0.42	0.09

Fig. 1. Application of supertree and supermatrix strategies for the phylogenetic reconstruction of paralogous genes. (a) Illustration of a hypothetical case where our method can be applied. In such a scenario gene duplications predated speciation events. (b) Schematic representation of the supertree (left) and supermatrix (right) framework for paralogs phylogenetic reconstruction. Each colour corresponds to genes from the same species and each row corresponds to 1-to-1 orthologous genes across species.

Fig. 2. Accuracy of the supertree and supermatrix topologies in the simulated datasets as compared to the real phylogenies. Average Robinson-Foulds distances per added alignment unit between the topologies for the 4 tested methods (Supertree-ME, Supermatrix-ME, Supertree-ML, Supermatrix-ML) and the reference phylogenetics trees in the simulated datasets.

Fig. 3. Effect of the supertree and supermatrix topologies on the empirical datasets. Average Robinson-Foulds distances per added alignment unit between the supertree and supermatrix distance-based topologies (Supertree-ME, Supermatrix-ME) without including mouse paralogs multiple sequence alignments and the RAxML trees computed only on the multiple sequence alignments of the mouse paralogs per family (ML-MOUSE).

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Software and data availability

All data, analyses, and results are available on Zenodo. The code and scripts have been deposited in GitHub (<https://github.com/athbaltzis/paralogs-nf>) and the container in (<https://hub.docker.com/r/athbaltzis/paralogs>).

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Author contributions

C.N., A.B. and L.M. designed the analysis, A.B. and L.M. carried out the validation and all the authors designed the validation procedure and wrote the manuscript.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.